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Gendered Subalternity and the Politics of Quiet Resistance: A Study of Female Agency in *Bitter Wormwood* by Easterine Kire

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Abstract:

This paper examines the portrayal of gender roles in Easterine Kire's *Bitter Wormwood*, focusing on the nuanced depictions of Naga women within the narrative dominated by political conflict and masculine violence. The novel primarily follows Mose's story against the backdrop of political strife; the female characters serve as moral anchors and bearers of cultural memory, often navigating their roles within patriarchal structures with resilience and quiet agency. By juxtaposing the overt masculinity of political resistance with the understated influence of women in the domestic and communal spheres, this study posits that Kire subtly critiques and redefines gendered power in Naga society. The paper also explores the absence of female political voices and the implications of this silence in the broader narrative of identity and resistance. These explorations will draw on postcolonial feminist theory, particularly Gayatri Spivak's concept of the subaltern.

Keywords: Writings in English from North East India, Easterine Kire, Gayatri Spivak, gender studies, feminist studies, female agency, subaltern, Naga political conflict, gendered subalternity.

Introduction

Easterine Kire's *Bitter Wormwood* offers a poignant and layered narrative set against the backdrop of Naga nationalism and conflict. The novel is set primarily in Kohima, Nagaland's capital, and spans from 1937 to 2007, tracing the life of Mose, the novel's protagonist. Mose's life begins marred by personal loss, as his father is crushed to death while felling a tree when Mose is only about seven months old. Having no male relatives in the immediate family, Mose grows under the care of his mother and his widowed paternal grandmother, with whom he forms powerful bonds. Though the novel follows Mose's journey through life amid the disturbing political strife that gripped Nagaland since the country's independence, the deeper undercurrents of the story emerge through the quiet yet profound presence of the female characters. Hence, the paper explores how Kire employs the domestic and emotional realms to highlight forms of gendered resistance, ultimately interrogating traditional notions of power and voice through the lens of postcolonial theory. In particular, it draws on Gayatri Spivak's concept of the subaltern to explore how Naga women in *Bitter Wormwood* navigate their marginalization and exercise agency within the confines of patriarchy and sociopolitical erasure.

Context to the Political Conflict

The India-Naga conflict is a long-standing and complex struggle, rooted in Naga people's demand for autonomy and self-determination in the Naga-inhabited regions of North East India. The desire for autonomy was expressed as early as 1918, when a group of educated Nagas, later known as the Naga Club, submitted a memorandum to the Simon Commission in 1929 asserting that "Nagas should not be included within the Reformed Scheme of India"(Pongro). Angami Zapu Phizo emerged as a central figure in the early Naga nationalist movement, leading efforts through the Naga National Council (NNC). He initiated talks with

the British Raj, advocating for the creation of a sovereign Naga nation. In June 1947, the NNC and representatives of the British administration signed a nine-point agreement which pledged to unify the Naga-inhabited areas under a single political and administrative unit. The agreement also acknowledged the Nagas' right to self-determination after a period of ten years. The interpretation of this agreement was vague, leading to disputes even within the NNC. On the day before India's Independence in 1947, the NNC, led by A.Z. Phizo, declared that the Naga-inhabited territory would remain an independent state and would not be part of the newly nation of India. The Indian government promptly rejected this claim.

The demand for autonomy continued peacefully until the 1950s, when the NNC launched a guerrilla movement. In response, the government of India deployed military forces, leading to a prolonged insurgency (Mujtaba). Meanwhile, Nagaland was established and officially recognized as the 16th state of the Indian Union on December 1, 1963. In 1975, the government of India and the NNC signed the Shillong Accord, a peace treaty. This agreement, however, triggered the formation of a more militant group, the NSCN (National Socialist Council of Nagaland), which later split into two factions in 1988. Peace talks between the NSCN and the Indian government, initiated in 1997, continue to the present day (Goswami).

The Naga political conflict has had a profound and lasting impact on the civilians, who were often caught between the clashes involving the Indian armed forces and the various Naga groups. Civilians have been caught in crossfire or have become victims of arbitrary arrests, torture, and extrajudicial killings. Despite recent peace talks and ceasefires, the situation remains complex, and many civilians continue to live in an atmosphere of uncertainty.

Easterine Kire weaves Mose's story against the backdrop of this political conflict. The trajectory of Mose's life runs parallel to the political conflict in Nagaland over the course of the novel.

The Gendered Landscape of Naga Society

Naga society follows a patriarchal and patrilineal structure, with male lineage and inheritance occupying a central role. Customary practices and traditions enforce strict gender roles, designating social and political discourse and decision-making as domains reserved exclusively for men. Customary laws, shaped and interpreted through a patriarchal lens, have historically excluded women from decision-making bodies. Though Naga women have traditionally played active roles in community life and agriculture, they have had limited access to formal political spaces. Within this context, social norms have confined them largely to domestic and reproductive roles (Jamir). However, these positions are also vital sites of cultural continuity and agencies for encoding values of resilience and strength for the community.

Kire's narrative reflects this sociocultural fabric of Nagaland, where traditional gender roles remain deeply rooted in cultural practices. Mose's mother and grandmother, and later his wife, emerge as pivotal figures- not through overt political action, but by embodying and passing on values of endurance, care and cultural identity.

Theoretical Framework

Drawing on Gayatri Spivak's seminal essay "Can the Subaltern Speak?", this paper explores how the women in *Bitter Wormwood* function as subalterns- individuals doubly marginalized by both postcolonial and patriarchal structures. The women characters of the novel do not participate in political discourse in the formal sense of active decision-making, but they exert influence in more subtle ways by shaping the moral compass of the male characters.

The domestic space serves as both a site of constraint and a space for subversion. As Spivak notes, the subaltern may not speak in the language of power, but readers can interpret her voice through her actions, choices, and cultural signifiers. The steadfast presence of the female

characters through periods of loss, upheaval and uncertainty offers a quiet counternarrative to the dominant male-centered discourse.

Gendered Silences as Subversive Resistance

A key theme in the novel is the strategic use of silence. Although silence is often interpreted as a symbol of oppression, Kire reclaims it as a space for strength, agency, and reflection. The political silence imposed on women contrasts with their meaningful presence in personal and communal life. In this context, silence may reflect a deliberate refusal to participate in violent systems or an assertion of an alternative form of wisdom.

For instance, Mose's grandmother Khrienuo and mother Vilau play crucial roles in his upbringing. He spends his childhood in a time of significant turbulence, including having to temporarily relocate to another village due to the Japanese invasion during World War II. Following the onset of the Naga-India conflict, frequent curfews disrupt everyday life, undermining the stability of the school system. Amid this chaos, Mose perceives the world around him as uncertain and tenuous- except for the unwavering support of his grandmother and mother. Khrienuo and Vilau assume the responsibility of caring for him, demonstrating quiet resilience as they withstand the strains of war and manage to eke out a livelihood in the absence of a male figure, traditionally regarded as the family's provider. Khrienuo philosophizes, "If life is hard to you, you simply harden yourself so its griefs are easier to bear. That is the only way to meet it" (Kire 22).

Vilau follows this same philosophy after a stray bullet fatally wounds Khrienuo while she tends her field. Rather than allowing the bitterness of this injustice to overwhelm her, Vilau chooses to focus her energy on domestic chores. She dedicates herself to caring for both her own house and that of her late mother-in-law, determined not to let Khrienuo's wrongful death destabilize the household that holds documents of historical importance. Her silent resilience in the face

of loss, injustice and militarized masculinity does not signal weakness but profound strength. By refusing to participate in cycles of violence, she asserts a quiet moral authority that shapes Mose's ethical outlook.

Similarly, Neilhounou, Mose's wife, chooses the quiet subversion of domesticity after her marriage with Mose. As a young girl, she once joined the Naga army and earned the nickname 'the rifle girl' for her sharpshooting skills. However, now she deliberately focuses on raising her daughter, whom she views as the bearer of a hopeful future. She deliberately avoids participating in political discussions during social meetings. For example, whenever Mose's friend, Neituo, comes over to give Mose news about the latest political developments, she deliberately busies herself with other household chores, refusing to be drawn back to a past she has chosen to walk away from. This refusal also represents her disillusionment with the male-dominated armed political struggle of the Naga army. Reflecting on the prolonged conflict, she contends:

“Twenty-one years without any respite. Or any lasting solutions. It was a man's war. If it had been left to the women, maybe they would have talked it over and sorted it out a long time back. After all, it was they who bore the brunt of the deaths of husbands, lovers, brothers and sons. On both sides. But women did not settle wars. It was unheard of” (Kire 113).

Although this statement reflects Neilhounou's personal view of the conflict and her growing disappointment with militarized violence as a solution, it can also be interpreted as author Easterine Kire's commentary on the silencing of women in male-dominated warfare, and from political dialogue. The statement emphasizes how women, despite suffering the deepest emotional losses during war, are systematically excluded in decision-making and peace processes. It critiques the patriarchal nature of conflict often described as “a man's war,” and

highlights the subversive resistance found in imagining an alternative where women, through empathy and dialogue, might have resolved the conflict differently. This speculative reflection challenges dominant narratives that valorize violence and marginalize women's voices, offering a quiet yet powerful vision of female agency.

In this way, Kire portrays silence as a form of resistance and agency, rather than passivity, using it to challenge both insurgent violence and gendered politics. The deliberate choice of silence by the female characters highlights the quiet strength and resilience of women as an alternative narrative to the dominant political discourse of violence.

Domestic Sphere as a Site of Resistance

In *Bitter Wormwood*, the domestic sphere is portrayed not as passive or apolitical but as a subtle yet potent site of resistance. Acts of care, the preservation of memory and culture, and emotional resilience become forms of resistance against the dehumanizing effects of conflict. Mose's grandmother and mother play crucial roles in preserving cultural identity and emotional resilience. Through storytelling, Khrienuo preserves intergenerational accounts of history against erasure by alternative narratives and histories. Both Khrienuo and Vilau endeavour to raise Mose with acute political consciousness. Vilau, for instance, buys a radio despite its high cost, recognizing its value as a means for learning about national and international political developments and educating Mose beyond the confines of their small town.

Khrienuo often discusses the unfolding political conflict with Mose, helping to shape his early political understanding. Although later, this role is taken up by his friend Neituo, it is the grandmother who lays the foundation for Mose's political awareness during their evening conversations. Every night after dinner, the three of them would huddle in the kitchen and listen to the radio, both mother and grandmother taking turns to ask Mose questions about the latest news, asking him to translate what he heard into their own native tongue. In this way, such

exercises positively enhance Mose's understanding of the political situation as well as his critical acumen.

Another insight into the historical trajectory of the Naga struggle for self-determination emerges with the discovery of some significant documents about the Simon Commission of 1927 and subsequent letters and agreements dating up to 1929, found in Khrienuo's hut after her death. This discovery highlights her role as a keeper of history. Her decision to leave the hut to Mose suggests she intended for him to uncover these documents. Through this quiet yet deliberate act of preservation, she becomes both a guardian and a conduit of historical memory.

By deliberately educating young Mose about the political conflict and actively passing historical knowledge to him, the domestic sphere becomes a site of resistance against the erasure of their history and cultural identity. In this way, the women in the novel play crucial roles in the politics of resistance.

Moreover, maintaining daily routines amid political upheaval and military repression can be understood as an assertion of humanity. In a society where violence threatens to define everyday existence, simply maintaining the rhythm of domestic life becomes an act of defiance. In the novel, it is particularly the female characters who ensure the continuity of normalcy within their domestic spheres. Despite an admitted sense of tension and fear, the women continued their daily activities, including working in the fields. They took care to be more watchful and cautious, fully aware of the constant threat of being shot at or being captured, tortured or raped by the armed forces. Kire narrates;

“The women did not loiter in the fields when they had finished for the day. There was such a sense of being watched that they hurriedly finished their work and prepared to go home” (Kire 70).

The fact that they continue their daily activity in this manner, albeit with caution, demonstrates their resolve not to buckle under the pressures of living in fear. Kire shows how ordinary people have the power to resist by choosing life over despair, asserting control over their private worlds when the public one is in chaos. This clearly indicates their agency.

In this way, Kire subtly but powerfully portrays the domestic sphere as a crucible of resistance. While the conflict unfolds in the public arena, individuals defend identity, memory, and dignity most valiantly within the private, intimate spaces of the home. Through these domestic spaces, Kire reclaims the power of the ordinary and the every day in resisting oppression and sustaining hope.

Patriarchal Constraints and Quiet Agency

The Naga society operates within a strict patriarchal framework that confines women largely to the domestic sphere. Men typically exclude women's opinions from political or social discourse, and society enforces rigidly defined gender roles. Kire's society in *Bitter Wormwood* also functions on the principle of this patriarchal foundation. This is illustrated, for instance, when Mose asks his mother to teach him how to cook so that he can ease his mother's load of daily chores. His mother responds, "Why? That is not men's work. Your father never cooked" (Kire 44). This suggestion by Mose seems outrageous to his mother, who has never heard of men cooking in the kitchen.

However, later in the novel, Kire attempts to dismantle the rigidity of gender roles when Mose and Neilhounuo become parents. Growing up, Mose did not have a male role model in his life, as he was raised by his mother and grandmother. Therefore, he struggles to manoeuvre the challenges of fatherhood. Similarly, Neilhounuo grew up without a mother, which made fulfilling the responsibilities of caring and nurturing challenging for her.

“Mose’s pattern of parenting was to be the “mother” to his daughter. He would think back on the way his mother had brought him up. Neilhounuo naturally became the strict parent” (Kire 111).

However, other than this instance, the society in *Bitter Wormwood* primarily operates within the framework of patriarchy. Mose’s mother Vilau, grandmother Khrienuo, wife Neilhounuo, and daughter Sabunuo are largely relegated to the domestic sphere, with marginal voices in the public space. Although the society is predominantly patriarchal, the female characters in the novel demonstrate quiet agency by holding their families and communities together. Their power is not overt or revolutionary, but it is steady and impactful. Their emotional resilience, wisdom, and moral clarity become forms of resistance to both patriarchy and militarism. Even though they lack institutional power, the female characters embody a gendered form of resistance that lies in their refusal to glorify violence, their insistence on preserving everyday life, and their ability to carry on in the face of overwhelming loss.

By highlighting their inner strength, Kire implicitly challenges the stereotype that portray women as passive victims of a history dominated by masculine violence. In doing this, Kire also redefines what it means to resist- and what it means to survive. Women navigate traditional gender expectations while exercising subtle influence within a rigid patriarchal structure. Thus, she challenges the idea that power must be overt or loud to be impactful.

Conclusion

Easterine Kire’s *Bitter Wormwood* offers a compelling reimagining of resistance through the lives of Naga women who, despite exclusion from formal political discourse, demonstrate profound moral and emotional strength. Through the characters of Khrienuo, Vilau, and Neilhounuo, Kire challenges dominant narratives of resistance rooted in violence and overt

political action. Instead, she foregrounds a quiet, gendered resilience expressed through care, memory, and silence.

Drawing on Gayatri Spivak's "Can the Subaltern Speak?", this essay has argued that Kire's female characters embody the subaltern position- doubly marginalized by both postcolonial and patriarchal structures. Spivak contends that the subaltern, particularly the female subaltern, cannot speak within hegemonic frameworks because her voice is not legible to dominant systems of power. Her speech is either co-opted or erased by dominant narratives that refuse to acknowledge agency in non-normative forms. While Kire's women characters do not engage in public political arenas, their actions resonate in other meaningful ways- preserving cultural memory, raising politically conscious children, and rejecting the cycle of violence. These forms of expression do not conform to dominant paradigms of power or speech but instead, form a counter-discourse that resists erasure. Kire's novel both challenges and affirms Spivak's contention that the subaltern cannot be heard unless mediated through dominant channels. On one hand, the women's resistance remains largely unacknowledged within formal political structures. On the other hand, Kire provides a literary space in which acts of endurance and moral clarity gain narrative centrality, thus creating a textual arena where readers may, in fact, read the subaltern - even if she cannot conventionally 'speak'.

The novel also redefines resistance not as a performative or vocal act but as a sustained commitment to survival, memory, and care amidst violence and instability. The domestic space, often dismissed as apolitical, emerges as a potent site of resistance in the novel. In maintaining the rhythms of everyday life, preserving cultural memory, and choosing compassion over violence, the women in Kire's narrative enact a quiet defiance against both militarism and insurgent aggression. Their refusal to participate in cycles of violence- most powerfully illustrated through Neilhounou's rejection of her past involvement in armed conflict- becomes

a radical act in itself. This kind of agency aligns with Spivak's call to reevaluate the epistemological framework through which we understand voice, power, and representation.

By examining the gendered subalternity of Kire's female characters through the lens of Spivak's theoretical framework, this essay underscores the necessity of expanding our definitions of resistance and political subjectivity. Silence, often misconstrued as passivity, is here reclaimed as a space of moral agency and resilience. In recognizing these quiet forms of resistance, *Bitter Wormwood* not only critiques the masculine violence both of the state and the insurgency but also offers a feminist reimagining of power- one that values endurance, ethical clarity, and the profound strength of women who persist in the face of historical and political erasure. Thus, the novel- and the women at its heart- invite us to reconsider the very question Spivak poses: not simply whether the subaltern can speak, but whether we are genuinely prepared to listen when she does so in ways that defy dominant modes of intelligibility.

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